

An Evaluative Report
on
***Addressing the Unequal Access to Education: Policy
Context, Challenges, and Recommendations***

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INTRODUCTION

In contemporary education, the problem regarding access to Higher Education (HE) remains very important because this factor influences the life ways of people and their general progress toward a better future. However, in spite of efforts towards promoting diversity, some latent disparities still persist, which prevent certain categories of youths from using up their full intellectual potential on attainment. Current status of Higher Education access is extremely uneven allowing educational disparities to continue and limiting opportunities for specific demographic categories. Firstly, this paper will focus on the policy issues concerning disparities in accessing HE. The process entails discussing the nuances of the problem, supportive evidence and suggestions for solutions. Afterwards, an in-depth review of past studies, and a review of current studies, would be a step towards developing theoretical outlooks that would elucidate this difficult concern of unequal availability. Finally, the paper will describe the challenges associated with this problem from professional persons who seek to solve it, recommend measures and consider the complexity of its execution. Lastly, the concluding part will provide an overview, summarizing the interconnection between the different aspects in the work.

POLICY CONTEXT

Different approaches have been formulated concerning the problem of uneven participation in college education that are aimed at leveling such a situation. They draw on tried and tested frameworks such as the National Curriculum and measures including Pupil Premium, which ensure firm basis for evidence. Increasing access to higher education should be an important policy priority, which should include tailored assistance, financial aid, and outreach efforts in order to reduce disparities (Kauffman, Hallahan and Pullen, 2017).

THE PROBLEM IN FOCUS

The unequal access has resulted into continuous gap with regard to access to higher learning leading to continued difference in the level of education attained. Therefore, this will be the issue in focus of this report. This topic will be based on evidence derived from investigating enrollment trends and academic achievement measures. In order to devise measures that are aimed at removing obstacles to access, policymakers make use of these metrics.

POLICY SOLUTIONS

Several measures have been included to address the challenge of disparity in getting university education degree. These include introducing policies such as monetary grants, outreach operations, and specialized help systems in order to address different barriers to higher education among underrepresented students (Wellington, 2015). The National Curriculum works as a policy framework in an attempt to promote inclusion; this includes providing a standardized basis for education. One other policy mechanism is Pupil Premium, whereby schools get some extra resources depending on the number of children in free school meals, orphans, adoptees, or service-personal children. This policy aims at curtailing the discrepancies that exist across schools regarding education.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This part of the literature review discusses numerous pieces of study focusing on unequal access to higher education. Researchers then focus on some marginalized groups and apply different conceptual perspectives in addressing the complexity of the problem. An investigation is guided by some reflective prompts regarding whom among the people involved may end up being unfairly disadvantaged, why they might suffer in this way, and what sorts of problems may or may not inhere in attempting to address such situations (Kauffman, Hallahan and Pullen, 2017).

DISADVANTAGED GROUPS

According to researches, such individuals who hail from lower socio-economic conditions are usually called worst off in matters pertaining to attaining higher education. Inability to draw on cultural capital, information barriers as well as restricted budget represent three types of impediments stopping individuals from participating in the competitive environment (Wellington, 2015). Many of these barriers present further challenges to people from disadvantaged social backgrounds.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS

Among the mentioned theoretical perspectives employed in these studies include social and economic theories, cultural capital, as well as critical pedagogy. Socio-economic theory implies that there is a close link between an individual's socioeconomic status and the education opportunities afforded them (Preston, 2016). Cultural capital is a process that concentrates on the importance associated with cultural awareness towards accomplishment of education objectives of various learners. Investigations on critical pedagogy look into how power relationships between education systems contributes to the repetition of inequality.

OBSTACLES IN ADDRESSING THE PROBLEM

Some of the past studies have aided in illuminating the challenges that present themselves when there is an attempt to equalize the openness to upper or tertiary level education. Among the recurrent themes found in this debate include; a lack of representation in school course work, financial burdens and poor outreach activities conducted with the population groups (Bantock,

2018). Furthermore, strong obstacles are provided by entrenched social values and prejudices which pervade the entire structure.

CHALLENGES IN PROFESSIONAL PRACTICE

This section is dedicated to recommending the goals of the policy on equal opportunities in higher education one more time and highlights possible pitfalls that educator might encounter during its implementation. These types of difficulties include limited resources, institutional resistance, and the need for cross-cultural sensitivity (Grigorenko, 2018). There should also be encouraged a culture of inclusivity in promoting increased uptake of such services, improvement of outreach programs, and provision of specific, targeted financial support.

BARRIERS IN PROFESSIONAL PRACTICE

There are many challenges faced by professionals engaged in the problem of unequal higher education access. One significant hindrance to distribution of scarce resources (including personal and financial) is present. These challenges are commonly encountered by educational institutions especially in deprived areas including limited funds, workforce shortage and lack of adequate facilities and infrastructure. Scattered programs cannot utilize the few available resources effectively to adequately provide concentrated, targeted social support for those who are affected by the economic setbacks. Additionally, these instructors find it problematic to offer help to learners who suffer from learning difficulties because of lack of necessary material and equipment. The lack of adequate funds and stiff resistance from the institutions creates immense challenges that face professional activity. Traditionally, education systems tend to remain committed to such things as old ways of teaching, curriculum, entry requirements for various colleges and so on. Fear of upsetting traditional arrangement in which they tend to be inflexible and stick to what they know may impair them in that. Thus the educators and the administrators must be very dedicated with a revolutionary mindset in order to change the system and create a more democratic education process challenging the conventional perspectives held by people (Bantock, 2018). In addition, the cultural issue of acceptance regarding correcting inequality complicates issues for professionals looking to do so. Standardized approaches fail to cater for many students who come from diverse

cultural perspectives, ethnicity, and socio-economic status, as well as hold divergent views or face unique challenges and issues. But if the educators choose to address the thought in question, they must do so sensitively and consider that culture plays a major role in determining the paths that pupils follow to learning. This can only be realized by making sure that educators undertake continuous professional development to enhance their cultural understanding and skills. Thus the school will ensure that every child is respected by creating an ambience where all children, whether the socio economic or culturally oriented ones get heard and supported (Eyisi, 2016). To overcome these hurdles, however, concerted efforts aimed at changing the design and ethos of education are required. The term entails having well-trained teachers capable of handling students' different needs.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PRACTICE

In reference to the stated challenges, an expansive and wide scale approach should be adopted. Some suggestions are:

- **Enhanced Outreach Programs:** One of the most critical recommendations focuses on designing and implementing holistic outreach programs. Such programs should transcend the ordinary recruiting practices, which are currently underway, and seek to disseminate information on university alternatives in areas, where such information is otherwise lacking. This will mean working closely with the community based organization, educational facilities as well as support agencies so as to ensure effectiveness of outreach initiatives. It should be noted here that prospective candidates come with different needs hence the need to share resources in various languages and formats (Grigorenko, 2018). If educational institutions improve their outreach programs, they will be able to preemptively interact as well as assist those who might not have thought about further education due to different obstacles.

- **Targeted Financial Support:** It is a matter of urgency to increase the number of diverse types of financial aid programs as well as extend their coverage, since the financial problems associated with obtaining a degree are very high. Therefore, specialized scholarships, grants and assistance funds should be instituted towards helping those who face problems related to social or economic circumstances (Wellington, 2015). The above financial assistance methods should not be limited to the amount required for paying the tuition fee but must extend to cater for other related expenses

such as books, residence fees and other living expenses. Therefore, it is essential for the government to provide an open-access procedure which makes eligible applicants easily get access without difficulties to those opportunities. Educational institutions can make it possible for under privilege people to be financially capable of pursuing their degrees and studies by alleviating the issue of financial constraints.

- **Fostering a Culture of Inclusivity:** It is vital to make deliberate efforts towards creating inclusive learning environments within institutions, which involves fostering an accepting culture that accepts students from diverse backgrounds. The suggestion is that there should be educators' and administrators' training initiatives focusing on understanding how to operate in a culturally sensitive way, being aware of how diverse groups of people are affected by school-related challenges. Instead, educators should be convinced to review and improve their teaching practices using in-service training sessions. It entails recognizing and embracing the divergent perspectives of students in the classroom. Furthermore, formation of support systems and establishment of mentorship programs inside the educational settings may help such students feel at home in such environments (Preston, 2016). The institutions build a conducive environment whereby every student is in a position to succeed irrespective of their social economic standing and cultural background through an inclusive climate. It is this environment that fosters creativity in learners, making them get more value out of learning experience (Kirkpatrick, 2016).

CONCLUSION

In summary, the problem of unequal access to higher education is multi-dimensional with far reaching effects on individual and society at large. The present paper has provided a thorough examination into the policy background, the theory of the issue, as well as challenges in my practice as a clinical psychologist of the problems related to this issue. Unfair accessibility of higher education has already become the most pressing issue, on which priority attention should be paid immediately. Critical analysis of selected policies and issues is used to highlight the importance of a comprehensive and collaborative strategy to close educational breaches. A holistic and cooperative approach is evidently required in order to dismantle the walls that are hindering the establishment of a hospitable educational system for everybody irrespective of his cultural heritage. This issue touches on ethics and is indeed a moral obligation and investment in the betterment of society. It will support social development, creativity and lead to an equitable tomorrow. Including people from different origins could improve our community as it would tap into underutilized potential of the individuals.

REFERENCE LIST

Bantock, G.H. (2018). *PAROCHIALISM OF THE PRESENT : contemporary issues in education*. ISBN 9781138220287.

Eyisi, D. (2016). The Usefulness of Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches and Methods in Researching Problem-Solving Ability in Science Education Curriculum. *Journal of Education and Practice*, [online] 7(15), pp.91–100. Available at: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1103224>.

Grigorenko, E.L. (2018). Creativity: a challenge for contemporary education. *Comparative Education*, 55(1), pp.116–132. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/03050068.2018.1541665>.

Kauffman, J.M., Hallahan, D.P. and Pullen, P.C. (2017). *Handbook of Special Education*. [online] *Google Books*. Taylor & Francis. Available at: https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=QDwIDwAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA16&dq=contemporary+issues+in+education&ots=qLynfd6aFb&sig=UE2Tz9RePyupSaKCLLlieqC3bc_4.

Kirkpatrick, R. (2016). *English Language Education Policy in Asia*. Cham Springer International Publishing.

Kleinig, J. (2016). *Philosophical issues in education*. London: Routledge.

Preston, D.S. (2016). *Contemporary issues in education*. Amsterdam: Rodopi.

Wellington, J. (2015). *Educational Research*. Bloomsbury Publishing.